

SpCA². As the dissociation of phenolic group decreases, it is natural that complex stability increases. It may further be noted that the interchange of position has little effect on log k_a value.

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Kinetics and Mechanism of Ruthenium(III) Chloride Catalysed Oxidation of Benzyl Alcohol by Hexacyanoferrate(III) Ion in Aqueous Alkaline Medium

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KINETICS of the oxidation of alcohols via catalysed or uncatalysed route are reported in much details. However, the ruthenium(III) chloride catalysed oxidation of benzyl alcohol by hexacyanoferrate(III) ion has not yet been studied. In the present study we have carried out the ruthenium(III) chloride catalysed oxidation of benzyl alcohol by hexacyanoferrate(III) ion in aqueous alkaline medium.

Experimental

The potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) was G. R. (S. Merck) grade and NaOH was BDH, AR grade. The solution of ruthenium(III) chloride was prepared by dissolving the sample in very dilute hydrochloric acid. The final strengths of HCl and RuCl₃ were kept at 16.38 × 10⁻² and 4.76 × 10⁻² M respectively. The sample of benzyl alcohol was BDH, AR grade and solution was prepared by weighing. The progress of reaction was followed by estimating the hexacyanoferrate(III) at different intervals of time. In all the kinetic runs the alcohol was kept in excess.

Results and Discussion

The reaction velocity follows zero order kinetics with respect to hexacyanoferrate(III) ion concentration. The oxidation rate which follows nearly first order kinetics with respect to lower concentration of the alcohols tends to zero order at higher concentration. Reaction rate goes on decreasing with

increasing hydroxide ion concentration. Reaction rate is directly proportional to the ruthenium(III) chloride concentration. A plot of 1/Rate vs [OH⁻] gives a straight line showing inverse proportionality of the rate with respect to hydroxide ion concentration. So, on the basis of aforesaid results, at lower alcohol concentration the reaction rate may be written as

$$-\frac{d[\text{Fey}]}{dt} = \frac{k[\text{Ru(III)}]_{\text{T}}[\text{S}]}{[\text{OH}^-]} \quad \dots (1)$$

where [Fey] represents [Fe(CN)₆]³⁻, [S] represents the alcohol concentration and k is a rate constant.

Reacting species of ruthenium(III) chloride in aqueous alkaline medium : Electronic spectral studies have confirmed that the ruthenium(III) chloride exists in the hydrated form¹ as [Ru(H₂O)₆]³⁺. Metal ions of the form [Ru(H₂O)₆]³⁺ are also known to exist as [Ru(H₂O)₅(OH)]²⁺ in alkaline medium^{2a}. In the present study it is quite probable that the species [Ru(H₂O)₅(OH)]²⁺ exists as [Ru(III)(OH)_x]^{3-x}. The value of x would always be less than six because there is no definite report of any hexahydroxy species^{2a} of ruthenium. The remainder of the coordination sphere will be filled by water molecule. Thus, all the ruthenium(III) chloride existing in the above form in aqueous alkaline medium will be the actual reacting species. It has been observed that the transition metal complexes are good abstracting agents for the hydride ion^{3,4}. The abstraction of α-hydrogen in acidic medium from 2-propanol has also been observed⁵. In a similar manner, Chatt *et al*⁶ concluded from their studies that the hydride ion transfer takes place from the α-carbon atoms of alcohol molecule or alkoxide ion. Therefore, one can safely conclude the abstraction of hydride ion from the alcohol molecule by ruthenium(III) in the present case also.

On the basis of the above the following scheme of oxidation is proposed.

The coordinated water molecule has been omitted for the sake of simplicity.

Considering the equilibrium condition for the complex formed in step I and knowing that

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$[\text{Ru(III)}]_{\text{T}} = \{[\text{Ru(III)(OH)}]^{2+} + [\text{Complex } C_1]\}$ the rate law obtained is

$$-\frac{d[\text{Fey}]}{dt} = \frac{2kK[\text{Ru(III)}]_{\text{T}}[\text{S}]}{[\text{OH}^-] + K[\text{S}]} \quad (2)$$

The rate law (?) apparently explains the experimental findings, i.e., first order kinetics with respect to catalyst, first order at lower alcohol and the retarding trend at higher alcohol concentration and the retarding trend due to hydroxide ion concentration.

At higher hydroxide ion and low alcohol concentrations the inequality $[\text{OH}^-] \gg K[\text{S}]$ holds good and equation (2) reduces to

$$-\frac{d[\text{Fe(CN)}_6]^{3-}}{dt} = \frac{2kK[\text{Ru(III)}]_{\text{T}}[\text{S}]}{[\text{OH}^-]} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

This clearly explains the inverse proportionality due to hydroxide ion and direct proportionality at lower alcohol concentrations. The value of kK at lower alcohol concentration was calculated as 17.5 min^{-1} .

In order to verify the rate law (2) for intermediate concentration of alcohol, the rate equation might be written as

$$\frac{1}{V_1} = \frac{[\text{OH}^-]}{2kK[\text{Ru(III)}]_{\text{T}}[\text{S}]} + \frac{1}{2k[\text{Ru(III)}]_{\text{T}}}$$

where, $V_1 = \frac{-d[\text{Fe(CN)}_6]^{3-}}{dt}$

A plot of $1/\text{Rate}$ vs $[\text{OH}^-]$ gives a straight line with positive intercept supporting the validity of the rate law.

A plot of $\frac{1}{V_1}$ vs $1/[\text{S}]$ gives a straight line with positive intercept on the $\frac{1}{V_1}$ axis. From the slope of straight line the value of kK was calculated and it was found to be 15.5 min^{-1} which is close to the value of kK obtained by equation (3). This is in agreement with the validity of the rate law (2) and supports the proposed reaction mechanism.

Stoichiometry and product study: The number of moles of hexacyanoferrate(III) ion consumed by one mole of benzyl alcohol was determined by taking a number of reaction mixtures in which the concentration of hexacyanoferrate(III) ion was kept ten times larger than benzyl alcohol concentration. After completion of the reaction, the remaining hexacyanoferrate(III) ion was estimated in different sets of experiment. In each set it was found that one mole of alcohol required 2 moles of hexacyanoferrate(III) ion. We, therefore, conclude that the final oxidation product would be benzaldehyde. The reaction mixture was distilled after completion of the reaction and the distillate collected at 177° gave a positive test with Schiff's reagent. On oxidation with alkaline potassium permanganate and further acidification by hydrochloric acid a white precipitate of benzoic acid formed which confirms that the final reaction product is benzaldehyde.

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Non-aqueous Oxidimetric Determination of Phenylhydrazides with Copper(II) in Acetonitrile

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COPPER(II) (in acetonitrile) is an excellent oxidant for use in redox titrations in acetonitrile medium¹. The oxidant possesses high redox potential, suitable stability and the ability to oxidise several compounds¹. Verma *et al* used this oxidant successfully for the determination of xanthates², organotrithiocarbonates³, ascorbic acid⁴, mercaptans⁴ and mercaptopyrimidines⁵ in acetonitrile medium. The use of copper(II) in acetonitrile has now been extended to the determination of phenylhydrazides. These compounds find important applications in medicine, agriculture, industry and in synthetic and analytical chemistry. The determination of these compounds is therefore of great interest and scope. Since these compounds are insoluble in water, the application of non-aqueous redox methods to their determination is advantageous. Most satisfactory results are obtained if copper(II) is titrated with the phenylhydrazide to be determined. Diphenylamine and diphenylbenzidine have been found suitable indicators in visual titrations. The initial blue colour changes to yellow at the end-point. The potentiometric titrations have been performed using an antimony or modified-calomel electrode as reference electrode and a bright platinum wire as indicator electrode. Phenylhydrazides are smoothly, rapidly and quantitatively oxidised with a two-electron change per